

Zone S: Auxiliary summary: Source > Function

Based on Carbo et al. (2025)

March 2025

This document, a companion to Carbo et al. (2025), samples lexical source meanings and their corresponding auxiliary functions from the Zone S auxiliary database, including both more lexical functions and more grammatical functions, to give an overview of grammaticalization patterns. Meanings and functions are derived based on grammatical descriptions (see Carbo et al. 2025 for source information). Some assumptions have been made in our attempt to unify “core” source meanings and auxiliary functions, for comparative purposes, but we have been relatively conservative in describing functions. Therefore, some items with separate functional entries may, in fact, be used similarly or identically across languages.

This document is not exhaustive, and, in particular, the absence of an attested auxiliary or function in a particular language (especially if other languages in the same cluster exhibit these auxiliaries) does not mean for certain that it does not occur in that language, or with that function.

Clusters are listed under their codes, with more information in the page footer.

Core source meaning	Core aux functions	Cluster	Guthrie Code	Language	Aux form	INF	SIT	SBJV / CSC	Notes
acquaint, become accustomed	habitual	S30	S33	Sesotho	tlwaela	Y			Possibly also past habitual when used with with perfective morphology (?)
			S32	Sesotho sa Leboa	tlwaetše (PFV of tlwaela)	Y			Past habitual, marked with PFV. We have not yet found it, but present tense <i>tlwaela</i> may also be used as a habitual.
able	ability (possibility)	S30	K21	Silozi	kona	Y			
			S31	Setswana	kgôna	Y			
			S33	Sesotho	kgona	Y			
		S40	S407	S. Ndebele	kghona	Y			Almost certainly a borrowing from Sotho-Tswana. Also found in Gauteng Zulu, at least, as <i>khona</i>
			S408	N. Ndebele	kxhona	Y	Y		
		S60	Gitonga	koja	Y				
	consecutive	S20	S21	Tshivenda	kona	Y		Y	

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already	always	S40	S41	isiXhosa	sólókò		Y		source: <i>sele</i> +cl 17 <i>oko</i> already+that (e.g. time) → function: 'always; constantly; persistently; continuously, all the time'	
annoy	do tiresomely, inappropriately, in desperation	S30	S33	Sesotho	tena		Y			
appear	just, merely	S40	S42	isiZulu	vele			Y	function: 'do from the outset; simply, just; do merely, do from the beginning'; <i>vela</i> : 'appear or come from ; appear, emerge'	
			S407	S. Ndebele	vele			?	function: 'of course, just'; <i>vela</i> : 'appear; be born'	
	necessity (+ just, merely?)	S40	S43	Siswati	vele		Y	Y	followed by: subjunctive or indicative including potential; cited function: 'should; must; undoubtedly, with good reason'; seems also to mean 'just, merely' based on online examples	
	when (time) [conjunction]	S40	S41	isiXhosa	bon'		Y		function: 'when a process occurred or will occur' source: <i>bonakala</i> 'appear' (i.e. be[come?] visible); followed by clausal complement	
arrive	before, first	S40	S42	isiZulu	fike			Y	'to do before (P&M); do before, do first, happen to do (Doke)'	
		S30	S33	Sesotho	fihla		Y	Y	'do something before anything else; act immediately, do straightway'	
	then	S40	S30	S31	Setswana	fitlha		Y		'on arrival, at this/that time'
			S43	Siswati	fika, efika			Y		'immediately after'
			S407	S. Ndebele	fike					
			S408	N. Ndebele	fike			Y	Y	

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arrive (at)	until	S30	S31	Setswana	fitlhêla		Y	Y	'until (S, C); until, in front of, preceding, foregoing, anterior (P)'	
			K21	Silozi	fetela		Y			
be(come)	relative tense / imperfective								found in all languages; semantically empty form employed for a number of functions; see spreadsheet for more details	
begin	begin	S30	S33	Sesotho	qala	Y			'begin to do'	
	begin, first	S40	S41	isiXhosa	qala	Y		Y	'started, first' (probably not distinct from other Nguni forms below)	
	first	S10 Sho na	S10	chiShona	taṅga			Y		'first'
			S40	S42	isiZulu	qale		Y	Y	'first; before; do on arrival'
				S43	Siswati	cale	Y		Y	'first, initially'
				S44	Ndebele (Zimbabwe)	qala			Y	'first'
bound	necessity	S30	S32	Sesotho sa Leboa	tlamegile	Y				
			S33	Sesotho	tlameha	Y				
		S50	S53	Xitsonga	boheka	Y				
(build?)	imperfective (habitual/continuous)	S30	S31	Setswana	aga		Y			
come	consecutive	S40	S41	isiXhosa	za			Y		
	until	S30	S31	Setswana	tla			Y		
			S32	Sesotho sa Leboa	tlê			Y		
		S40	S42	isiZulu	ze			Y		
			S43	Siswati	te			Y		
	until?	S40	S407	S. Ndebele	ze					
	upon X's return	S10 Sho na	S10	chiShona	uya			Y		
	eventually	S40	S408	N. Ndebele	te			Y		

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	finally, until	S40	S44	Ndebele (Zimbabwe)	ze			Y	
	future	S30	S32	Sesotho sa Leboa	tla	Y			
		S40	S44	Ndebele (Zimbabwe)	za	Y			
	do well; apprehensive/avertive?	S30	S33	Sesotho	tla			Y	
	surprise, disgust	S40	S43	Siswati	za			Y	
	habitual	S30	S31	Setswana	tlê			Y	
	imperative	S40	S41	isiXhosa	ze			Y	
	possibility	S30	S31	Setswana	tla			Y	
purpose	S30	S33	Sesotho	tlilo	Y				
come+NEG	never	S40					Y		may be common at least across Nguni (we have details for at least S. Ndebele, Ndebele (Zimbabwe), N. Ndebele, Xhosa) – tense may vary? All we have data for are followed by SBJV Swati has neg+com (<i>ngete</i>) meaning ‘negative future’, followed by INF or SBJV
come from	do futilely and without end; act meanwhile/afterwards	S30	S33	Sesotho	tswa		Y		
	immediately	S10 Shona	S10	chiShona	bva		Y		
	meanwhile	S50	S53	Xitsonga	pfã		Y		
	of nature, always	S40	S41	isiXhosa	vela		Y		
	without reason; just, merely	S40	S41	isiXhosa	vela			Y	
common (be); abound	habitual	S40	S407	S. Ndebele	vame	Y			dictionary describes as “adj. general, prevalent”

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			S42	isiZulu	vama	Y			
continue, keep on	continuous	S30	K21	Silozi	swala	Y	Y		
copula+APPL	continuous	S30	S31	Setswana	nna; ntse		Y		
copula	continuous	S60	S62	Gitonga	ba		Y		Lanham is very certain that na is the original form, and ba and ra recent grammaticalizations
					na		Y		
					ra		Y		
	past	S30	S31	Setswana	nê		Y		
	since	S30	S31	Setswana	le		Y		
	sometimes	S30	S31	Setswana	nê		Y		
dawn?	continuous without success	S40	S43	Siswati	sa		Y		
dawn+NEG?	not yet	S30	S32	Sesotho sa Leboa	ešo			Y	
die+NEG	never (rule out the possibility)	S10 Sho na	S10	chiShona	fa		Y		
die for	necessity	S60	S62	Gitonga	fela	Y			is this different from other <i>felas</i> ?
do, make	do the right thing	S20	S21	Tshivenda	ita		Y		
end	continuous	S30	S31	Setswana	fêla		Y		note that difference between 'end' and 'finish' is not completely clear in all cases
	in fact	S30	S33	Sesotho	fela (fêla)		Y	Y	
	just, merely		S30	S31	Setswana	fêla		Y	
			S40	S408	N. Ndebele	phela		Y	
	just, merely; sometimes	S40	S407	S. Ndebele	phele				
	keep on; sometimes	S40	S408	N. Ndebele	phele			Y	difference between phele & phela uncertain
only	S30	S32	Sesotho sa Leboa	fêla		Y		(similar to just, merely?)	
end by	in the end	S10	S10	chiShona	dzimara			Y	
	result	Sho na			dzimara		Y		
extinguish	almost	S40	S42	isiZulu	cishe	Y		Y	

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			S43	Siswati	cishe				Meaning of source to be checked
fight (encircle & attack)	during this year	S30	S31	Setswana	dika		Y		?
finish	finish	S30	S33	Sesotho	qeta	Y			note that difference between 'end' and 'finish' is not completely clear in all cases
		S40	S407	S. Ndebele	qeda	Y			
	last (i.e. most recently?)	S40	S41	isiXhosa	gqibela	Y			
	then	S40	S42	isiZulu	qede			Y	
	ultimately	S40	S41	isiXhosa	phetha			Y	
when, just after	S40	S41	isiXhosa	khova	Y				
finish?	as soon as	S30	K21	Silozi	mana	Y			(see also 'stand with?')
follow closely?, continu	inevitable	S40	S43	Siswati	jinge			Y	
forget; delay	continuous	S40	S42	isiZulu	libele		Y		do continuously what ought not to be done
fright, get/have	happen to, chance to	S30	K21	Silozi	suha / suhana	Y	Y		
	suddenly	S40	S407	S. Ndebele	thuke				
			S408	N. Ndebele	thuke		Y		
			S43	Siswati	etfuka, tfuka		Y		
suddenly; unexpectedly	S30	S33	Sesotho	tshoha (tšōha)		Y			
full, abundant	likely, often, always	S50	S53	Xitsonga	tála	Y			
go	habitual	S30	S33	Sesotho	ye				
		S40	S43	Siswati	ye			Y	
	just, merely	S40	S41	isiXhosa	ye			Y	
	past	S40	S41	isiXhosa	ye			Y	
	progression; occasionally	S40	S41	isiXhosa	ya		Y	Y	
go (away), walk	continuous	S30	S31	Setswana	tsamaya		Y		
	go about doing?	S40	S42	isiZulu	hambe		Y		
	often (habitual?)	S40	S43	Siswati	hambe		Y		see also Xitsonga <i>hámba</i> 'always, continually', given without a lexical source

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	until	S30	S31	Setswana	tsamaya		Y	Y	'until' meaning only found with infinitive form of <i>tsamaya</i> , i.e. <i>go tsamaya</i>
go away	do rashly, unexpectedly, regrettably; afterwards, soon, eventually	S30	S33	Sesotho	tlōha		Y		
	soon	S30	K21	Silozi	tuha		Y		
go out	reason	S30	S31	Setswana	tswa				
go round	continuous; habitual	S10 Sho na	S10	chiShona	pota		Y		
go?+PFV	past? (PFV)	S30	S32	Sesotho sa Leboa	ile			Y	
		S30	S31	Setswana	ilê				
	purpose	S30	S33	Sesotho	ilo = ile + inf	Y			
hate	intention	S40	S42	isiZulu	zondelele	Y			<i>zonda</i> 'hate'
hunt	intention	S40	S42	isiZulu	zingela, zingele	Y			
hurry	quickly	S30	K21	Silozi	pakisa	Y	Y		
		S40	S41	isiXhosa	khawuleza			Y	
					tshetsha	Y		Y	
	quickly, soon	S50	S53	Xitsonga	hàtla		Y		
		S30	S33	Sesotho	phakisa		Y	Y	
		S40	S43	Siswati	sheshe, shesha			Y	
					phange			Y	
soon, immediately	S40 Sot ho- Tsw ana	S31	Setswana	akofa		Y			
increase	again	S30	K21	Silozi	ekeza	Y	Y		
		S50	S53	Xitsonga	èngeta, engete		Y		
	exceed expectations; do further	S30	S33	Sesotho	eketsa			Y	
	often	S30	K21	Silozi	atisa	Y			
			S33	Sesotho	atisa	Y			

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know	ability	S40	S407	S. Ndebele	kwazi	Y			'know' verbs have different modal scope in different languages
			S408	N. Ndebele	wati	Y			
			S41	isiXhosa	kwazi	Y			
			S42	isiZulu	kwazi	Y			
			S43	Siswati	ati	Y			
		S50	S53	Xitsonga	tiva	Y			
		S30	S32	Sesotho sa Leboa	tseba	Y			
lack	until	S50	S53	Xitsonga	kála; ká			Y	
lead	further (continuation of narrative)	S40	S41	isiXhosa	qokélà			Y	
leave	after	S40	S407	S. Ndebele	suke			Y	
			S408	N. Ndebele	suke/suka		Y	Y	
	already	S40	S408	N. Ndebele	sele		Y		
	because	S40	S42	isiZulu	suke		Y		
	by chance; unexpectedly	S50	S53	Xitsonga	tshika		Y		
	just, merely	S40	S42	isiZulu	suke			Y	
	just, merely; surprise	S40	S41	isiXhosa	suka			Y	
	immediately after	S30	S32	Sesotho sa Leboa	tloga				
	shortly (t)hereafter	S30	S31	Setswana	tloga		Y		
	then	S40	S43	Siswati	suka, esuka				
soon	S20	S21	Tshivenda	tuwa		Y	Y		
stop	S30	S33	Sesotho	tlohela	Y				
leave behind	extremely	S40	S41	isiXhosa	shiya			Y	
like	almost	S40	S42	isiZulu	thanda	Y			
	like to	S30	S33	Sesotho	rata	Y			
	want	S40	S408	N. Ndebele	thanda	Y			
long ago	far(?) past continuous	S40	S43	Siswati	kadze				<i>De</i> 'long' is an adjective; <i>ka-</i> is an adverbial marker
	past (once)	S40	S408	N. Ndebele	kade		Y		
long?	until?	S40	S41	isiXhosa	de			Y	

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meet with by chance	unexpected result (mirative)	S10 Sho na	S10	chiShona	yerekana		Y			
mutiply (grow, increase)	immediate past	S40	S42	isiZulu	sanda	Y			<i>anda</i> 'multiply' prefixed with persistive <i>sa-</i>	
			S44	Ndebele (Zimbabwe)	sanda				<i>anda</i> 'grow, increase'	
need	necessity	S30	S33	Sesotho	hloka	Y			need > necessity found in many other languages, not always listed as aux in grammars, v. lexical	
neg+have	after	S30	S31	Setswana	se-na / sena	Y				
not taking	not yet / not at all	S30	S31	Setswana	ise		Y	Y		
overcome, be	inability	S40	S408	N. Ndebele	bhalelwa	Y				
pass, surpass	consecutive	S30	S31	Setswana	feta			Y		
	do nonetheless	S40	S42	isiZulu	dlule			Y		
place, put	in course of time	S30	S32	Sesotho sa Leboa	bea			Y		
quickly	quickly	S40	S42	isiZulu	sheshe			Y	lexical	
	at the right time	S30	S31	Setswana	jafilê			Y		
quotative	if, when, then	S30	S31	Setswana	re		Y			
	in vain; fail	S10					Y			
	introductory	Sho na	S10	chiShona	ti			Y		
	occasionally	S30	K21	Silozi	ti		Y			
	seem	S40	S43	Siswati	shangatsi		Y			
	time, preconditions	S40	S41	isiXhosa	thi				followed by indicative, including potential	
	to such an extent	S40	S41	isiXhosa	tsho			Y		
	until	S30	K21	Silozi	te			Y		
	when	S40	S408	N. Ndebele	ri			Y		
	while	S40	S43	Siswati	tsi				also followed by indicative	
	yet		S10 Sho na	S10	chiShona	ti		Y		

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	a little	S40	S42	isiZulu	thi		Y		
	when	S40	S42	isiZulu	thi	Y			
quotative (+ potential)	seem	S40	S41	isiXhosa	nga+thi		Y		
reach	until	S50	S53	Xitsonga	kóndza		Y		
refuse	continuous	S10 Sho na	S10	chiShona	ramba		Y		
	negation	S30	S32	Sesotho sa Leboa	gana	Y			
	as soon as	S30	S33	Sesotho	hana	Y			lexical source assumed
refuse, deny	just, merely	S40	S42	isiZulu	phike				
refuse, dispute	continuous; always	S50	S53	Xitsonga	phika	Y			
	after	S30	S32	Sesotho sa Leboa	šala		Y		
remain	after a separation	S10 Sho na	S10	chiShona	sara		Y		
	already	S30	S31	Setswana	sêitse (C), setswe (S)		Y		
		S40	S407	S. Ndebele	se				Y
			S41	isiXhosa	sele/se		Y		
	already, now	S30	S33	Sesotho	se		Y		
	continuous	S30	S33	Sesotho	sala, salla	Y	Y		Chaphole 1998:199: salla –looks like a typo of the author's
	meanwhile	S30	S31	Setswana	sala		Y	Y	
	necessity	S40	S42	isiZulu	sale		Y		This may not be a common use
			S43	Siswati	sale		Y		
	then	S30	S31	Setswana	sale			Y	
			S407	S. Ndebele	sale				
		S40	S408	N. Ndebele	sala?		Y		
	then, meanwhile	S40	S42	isiZulu	sale			Y	
usually; no more	S40	S408	N. Ndebele	hlwe, hlwa		Y		when negated "no more" Z p 155	
already? past?	S30	S32	Sesotho sa Leboa	šetše		Y			
remain?	already	S30	K21	Silozi	se		Y		se auxes possibly also from sala?

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	exclusive	S40	S43	Siswati	se		Y		
			S44	Ndebele (Zimbabwe)	se		Y		
		S40	S42	isiZulu	se				
repeat	again	S20	S21	Tshivenda	dovha	Y	Y	Y	
		S30	S33	Sesotho	phēta		Y	Y	
		S40	S41	isiXhosa	phinde			Y	
			S42	isiZulu	phinde			Y	
			S43	Siswati	phindze			Y	
			S44	Ndebele (Zimbabwe)	phinde			Y	
required	necessity	S40	S41	isiXhosa	funeka		Y	Y	
resemble	just, merely	S40	S43	Siswati	fane				
	necessity	S30	K21	Silozi	swanela	Y			
	possibility	S30	K21	Silozi	swana		Y	Y	
	probably	S40	S41	isiXhosa	fana	Y			
	weak necessity?	S30	S33	Sesotho	tshwanela	Y			
return	again	S30	K21	Silozi	buela	Y		Y	
			K21	Silozi	kuta		Y		
			S33	Sesotho	boela			Y	
		S40	S407	S. Ndebele	buye			Y	
			S408	N. Ndebele	buya			Y	
			S42	isiZulu	buye			Y	
			S44	Ndebele (Zimbabwe)	buya				
	again, eventually	S40	S43	Siswati	buye, buya			Y	
	again; regularly	S40	S41	isiXhosa	buya	Y		Y	
	also, again	S50	S53	Xitsonga	tlhèlà		Y		
	experiential	S20	S21	Tshivenda	vhuya		Y	Y	
	instead (contrary to what is right or expected)	S10 Shona	S10	chiShona	dzoka		Y		
	next	S40	S42	isiZulu	buye			Y	
return to	again	S60	S62	Gitonga	ḽwelela		Y		

S20 Venda ; S30 Sotho-Tswana; S40 Nguni; S50 Tsonga; S60 Copi

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rise	stand up, rise (for/to do)	S30	S33	Sesotho	tsohela	Y			
rise+COMP	whatever, whenever	S40	S41	isiXhosa	sukuba		Y		
rise early	tomorrow; soon	S10 Sho na	S10	chiShona	fuma		Y		
rise; wake up; get up	in the morning, early	S30	S31	Setswana	tšoga		Y		
				Setswana	tsogile		Y		
			S33	Sesotho	tsoha		Y		
satisfy	favourable set of circumstances	S40	S41	isiXhosa	kholisa			Y	
	habitual, usually	S40	S41	isiXhosa	kholisa	Y	Y		
			S42	isiZulu	kholisa	Y			
seem, be like	likely, probable	S10 Sho na	S10	chiShona	ṅge				followed by relative clause (not really auxiliary)
	tense	S10 Sho na	S10	chiShona	ṅge / ṅga (dialectal)		Y		
sleep	spend the night (doing)	S20	S21	Tshivenda	lala		Y		
		S30	S31	Setswana	lala, lêtse		Y		
			S32	Sesotho sa Leboa	lala		Y		
		S33	Sesotho	lala		Y			
	during the night	S30	K21	Silozi	lobala		Y		
spend the day	spend the day; continuous/continually	S20	S21	Tshivenda	ṭwa		Y		
		S30	S32	Sesotho sa Leboa	hlwa				
	spend the day	S20	S21	Tshivenda	ṭwela	Y			
	spend the day (pfv)	S30	S31	Setswana	tlhôtse		Y		
	imperfective	S30	S31	Setswana	tlhôla		Y		
	no longer	S30	S31	Setswana	tlhole		Y		this is the sense under negation
spend time	always, continuous	S50	S53	Xitsonga	dzumba		Y		
	continuous	S30	K21	Silozi	tola		Y		
	long ago	S10 Sho na	S10	chiShona	ṅguva		Y		

Zone S: Auxiliary summary: Source > Function

Based on Carbo et al. (2025)

March 2025

Core source meaning	Core aux functions	Cluster	Guthrie Code	Language	Aux form	INF	SIT	SBJV / CSC	Notes
spoil	rather	S10 Shona	S10	chiShona	iṣa		Y		
stand for	intend to	S40	S408	N. Ndebele	jamisela	Y			
	just, merely	S40	S43	Siswati	mane		Y	Y	"different forms" (Taljaard et al. 1991: 156); subjunctive, indicative, participial (in negative) (Ziervogel & Mabuza 1976: 120)
	necessity	S40	S407	S. Ndebele	mele	Y		Y	
		S40	S41	isiXhosa	mel(w)e	Y		Y	
		S40	S42	isiZulu	mele; melwe	Y		Y	
often	S40	S41	isiXhosa	mana	Y	Y			
stand with (stand+RECIP) (?)	just, merely	S40	S43	Siswati	mane		Y	Y	"different forms" (Taljaard et al. 1991: 156); subjunctive, indicative, participial (in negative) (Ziervogel & Mabuza 1976: 120)
			S407	S. Ndebele	mane		Y		source meaning not given
			S42	isiZulu	mane		Y		(related? Meaning given as 'stop, halt', which might also be a logical extension)
	often	S40	S41	isiXhosa	mana	Y	Y		
stand-NEG	never	S40	S43	Siswati	mange				Ziervogel & Mabuza (1976: 120, 157) suggest e ending is in analogy to other aux's, despite source in neg. - anga.
stay	afterwards	S40	S41	isiXhosa	sala		Y		
	if, when, then (?)	S40	S43	Siswati	hleze				probably a borrowing from Zulu
	always	S30	S32	Sesotho sa Leboa	dula		Y		
		S40	S42	isiZulu	hleze		Y		
		S50	S53	Xitsonga	tsháma		Y		
	constantly	S40	S44	Ndebele (Zimbabwe)	hlezi		Y		
continue	S30	S33	Sesotho	dulela	Y				

Zone S: Auxiliary summary: Source > Function

Based on Carbo et al. (2025)

March 2025

Core source meaning	Core aux functions	Cluster	Guthrie Code	Language	Aux form	INF	SIT	SBJV / CSC	Notes
	continue, continuous, always ?	S30	S31	Setswana	nna		Y	Y	
	continuous	S40	S41	isiXhosa	hlala		Y		
			S43	Siswati	hlala		Y		
	continuous; habitual	S10 Sho na	S10	chiShona	gara		Y		
	continuous; habitual	S40	S42	isiZulu	hlale		Y		
	habitual	S30	S31	Setswana	nne				
	habitual	S40	S407	S. Ndebele	hlale				
	immediately	S40	S44	Ndebele (Zimbabwe)	hle			Y	
spend the day; repeatedly, permanently	S30	S33	Sesotho	hlòla		Y			
stay for (stay+APPL)	always	S40	S42	isiZulu	hlalele	Y			
	always, continually	S40	S408	N. Ndebele	hlalela	Y			
	ready	S40	S41	isiXhosa	hlalele, hlelele	Y			
stop	hortative	S10 Sho na	S10	chiShona	rega			Y	hortative meaning when used in infinitive, followed by subjunctive. Otherwise, means 'stop'
	stop	S30	S32	Sesotho sa Leboa	lesa	Y			
straight (be, go)	intend to	S40	S33	Sesotho	lesa	Y			
			S43	Siswati	condze	Y			
stretch	really	S30	S42	isiZulu	qonde	Y			
			S31	Setswana	nama, namilê		Y	Y	
strike	cause; such that	S40	S41	isiXhosa	betha			Y	
	completely	S40	S42	isiZulu	shaya, shaye		Y		
strike with	future negative	S30	S31	Setswana	kitla, ketla		Y		
strong	be inclined to	S40	S43	Siswati	cinele				

Zone S: Auxiliary summary: Source > Function

Based on Carbo et al. (2025)

March 2025

Core source meaning	Core aux functions	Cluster	Guthrie Code	Language	Aux form	INF	SIT	SBJV / CSC	Notes	
subsequently do	recently	S40	S41	isiXhosa	sandula	Y			apparently persistent <i>sa-</i> plus <i>andula</i> , but basic meaning unclear (<i>andulela</i> (applicative form means 'go before, precede') isiXhosa also has <i>andula</i> + inf, subjv ;meaning 'consecutive' (also aux-like); cf. isiZulu <i>anda</i> 'multiply'??	
sufficient	as soon as	S40	S42	isiZulu	nele (anele?)			Y		
	immediately	S40	S44	Ndebele (Zimbabwe)	nela	Y			no lexical source noted	
	just as?	S40	S407	S. Ndebele	nele				meaning not totally clear; source assumed to be <i>anela</i>	
	just, merely	S40	S44	Ndebele (Zimbabwe)	anela					
	only, just	S40	S42	isiZulu	anela, anele, (nele)	Y				
suitable, appropriate	necessity	S30	K21	Silozi	lukela	Y				
			S31	Setswana	tšhwanêla	Y		Y		
			S32	Sesotho sa Leboa	swanetše	Y				
		S40	S407	S. Ndebele	fanele	Y		Y		
			S408	N. Ndebele	fanele	Y		Y		
			S41	isiXhosa	fânèlè	Y		Y		
			S42	isiZulu	fanele			Y		
			S43	Siswati	fanele	Y		Y		
S60	S62	Gitonga	yela	Y						
surprise	must not	S50	S53	Xitsonga	tshuki				(negated form) (likely also followed by situative)	
	possibility	S50	S53	Xitsonga	tshùkà		Y			
take to, for? (take+APPL)	immediately	S60	S62	Gitonga	jegela	Y				
tell?	not in a long time / long time after	S30	S31	Setswana	bolo (bôlo)	Y	Y			

Zone S: Auxiliary summary: Source > Function

Based on Carbo et al. (2025)

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throw	almost	S40	S42	isiZulu	phonse, phose	Y	Y	similar forms also meaning 'almost', without
								lexical meanings given: S. Ndebele S407 <i>pheze</i> N. Ndebele S408 <i>phase, phoswe, phoso</i>

Zone S: Auxiliary summary: Source > Function

Based on Carbo et al. (2025)

March 2025

Core source meaning	Core aux functions	Cluster	Guthrie Code	Language	Aux form	INF	SIT	SBJV / CSC	Notes
									isiXhosa S41 <i>phantsa</i> , <i>phantse</i> Xitsonga <i>phosa</i> (borrowing?)
		S40	S43	Siswati	phose	Y		Y	
		S40	S44	Ndebele (Zimbabwe)	phose			Y	
travel	later, then, while, continue	S30	S31	Setswana	êta		Y		
use quickly	beforehand	S40	S41	isiXhosa	phanga	Y		Y	
wait	wait to	S30	S32	Sesotho sa Leboa	diega	Y			
wait for someone	always	S50	S53	Xitsonga	tshámala (L&H); tshamela (Baumbach)	Y			
wander about	habitual	S40	S42	isiZulu	zinge		Y		
	about to	S40	S42	isiZulu	funa	Y		Y	
want	almost	S30	K21	Silozi	bata	Y	Y		
			S31	Setswana	batla	Y	Y	Y	
				Setswana	rata	Y	Y	Y	
				Setswana	senka	Y	Y	Y	
			S33	Sesotho	batla	Y	Y		
	S60	S62	Gitonga	haja	Y				
	want, desire	S40	S408	N. Ndebele	funa	Y			
		S30	S32	Sesotho sa Leboa	rata	Y			
S33			Sesotho	lakatsa	Y				
necessity	S30	S33	Sesotho	hloka	Y			also listed under 'need'	
wanted (be)	necessity	S40	S407	S. Ndebele	funeke				in our investigations, not widespread as a modal in S. Ndebele (TC)
			S408	N. Ndebele	funeka			Y	
			S43	Siswati	funeka			Y	

For additional information, including references: Carbo, Matilda, Thera Marie Crane & Hilde Gunnink. 2025. 'Comparative auxiliary spreadsheet for Southern Bantu languages.' DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15143755